

ON SLIDING FRICTION OF PEEL-PLY TEXTURED EPOXY RESIN SURFACES CONTAMINATED BY AIRCRAFT OPERATING FLUIDS

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1 Introduction

Research and technology projects on aircraft fuselage pursue the application of lightweight materials to endeavour improved structural efficiency. Especially thermoset fibre reinforced plastics (FRPs) comply with the designer's need for excellent specific material properties. Structural designs applying such composite materials need to satisfy the authorities airworthiness code for 'equivalent level of safety' [1].

Due to plastic deformation capacity of state-of-the-art metallic fuselage designs, those certification requirements are achieved almost naturally by the design's intrinsic energy absorption capabilities. In contrast to metallic materials, thermoset FRPs exhibit brittle fracture behaviour when loaded beyond their elastic limits. Thus energy absorption by plastic deformation is unsatisfactorily limited. Considering FRP physical properties, however, encourage alternative principles of energy absorption, such as friction.

Generally, sliding friction is subject to minimisation as it causes energy loss and material loss [2]. In contrast, the purpose of energy absorption requires energy and material loss. In order to meet the demands the coefficient of friction needs to be sufficiently high to efficiently transform mechanical work into friction energy.

When composite materials are investigated in friction applications, they are commonly paired with metallic surfaces [3]. Therein, the possibility to tailor the composite properties using special fillers with different volume fraction, shape, and size is of special interest [4].

However, few information is available about polymer-on-polymer friction. Bartenev and Lavrentev [5] present data showing the friction

coefficient of a polymer-on-polymer pair being higher than for friction on metallic surfaces. For polyvinylchloride a coefficient of friction of 0.41 is presented. It was found that for rigid polymers, the friction coefficient depends upon the nature of the rigid surface.

Currently, one publication is known to the authors covering textured epoxy resin surface in a tribological investigation. Schön [6] has explored reciprocal sliding for composite on composite contact in order to model bolted joints and predict the corresponding failure load. The initial coefficient of friction recorded was 0.65 and 0.74 after wear in. However, integrating energy absorption attributes based on sliding friction into carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) aircraft fuselage design requires knowledge about the governing mechanism. In order to determine important features of a feasible design, major influencing parameters such as the surface characteristic or surface contamination are in focus. Therefore the present paper investigates effects of texture and contamination by aircraft operating fluids on the sliding friction response of polymer surfaces. It specifically addresses epoxy resin surfaces of continuous fibre reinforced composite material [7] currently applied in aircraft industry. Peel-ply [8] was utilised to achieve characteristic surface texture.

A pin-on-flat type test apparatus in compliance with ASTM D1894 [9] is employed determining the friction coefficient as a function of both, the initial surface texture and the contamination by three different aircraft operating fluids (e.g. de-icing fluids and engine oil). Special attention is drawn to the texture orientation of the resin surface as well as to the orientation of reinforcing fibres in the surface layer.

The pin-on-flat sliding friction results considering textured surfaces contaminated by aircraft operating fluids are novel in the field of polymer-on-polymer friction.

2 Experimental Procedure

In this section the specimen preparation, the pin-on-flat test apparatus, and testing conditions are explained comprehensively.

2.1 Specimen Preparation

All specimens of the present contribution were made from HexPly[®]8552/35%/194/AS4 with a nominal cured ply thickness of 0.185 mm. The samples were manufactured from unidirectional prepreg material following the processing recommendations by the supplier [7]. For all specimens a (0/90/0)_s stacking sequence was chosen. In order to avoid excessive warpage distortions, the authors complied with Stefaniak et al. [10] and Kappel et al. [11] in CFRP plate fabrication. This included for example the vacuum bagging as depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Vacuum bagging for sample manufacturing.

Prior to use of the aluminium tool the surface was cleaned and degreased with acetone before applying the liquid release agent Chem-Trend Chemlease[®] for three times.

The prepreg stacks were laminated by hand, applying the vacuum bagging arrangement illustrated, for autoclave curing. In the layup process each individual ply was aligned using a steel ruler and compacted with a hand roller. For the textured surface a polyamide fabric peel-ply HexForce[®]T0089 [8] was applied such that the warp direction aligned with surface layer fibre orientation. After demolding and peel-ply removal, the specimens were machine ground to circular shape using diamond grinding points with granulation D91. The machining parameters were set to 5 mm/s feed

rate and 50,000 revolutions per minute. Fig. 2 depicts the resulting edge quality.

Fig. 2. Peel-ply textured surface and corresponding edge quality after machining.

A circular specimen shape was selected in order to reduce edge effects during the experiments. In contrast to the use of a rectangular shape, the risk of specimen tilting around the foremost edge, was minimised. This is especially beneficial for data quality at the onset of sliding friction, where any elastic deformation in the test rig could otherwise enforce specimen tilting.

Fig. 3. Peel-ply textured surface after cleaning procedure.

The average surface area was determined as $102.78 \pm 1.26 \text{ mm}^2$ by microscopic measurement of ten random samples.

Before testing, the surfaces were cleaned with acetone to remove grease and release agent residues from the manufacturing process. Additionally,

remaining debris was eliminated by blowing pressurised air across the surface. The surface purity was observed microscopically and is presented in Fig. 3 for the peel-ply textured specimens.

2.2 Pin-on-flat Test Apparatus

A pin-on-flat test apparatus was employed determining the friction coefficient. It is designed in compliance with [9] and is depicted in Fig. 4.

The apparatus features two linear bearings (1) and a flat aluminium plate (3) resting on ball bearings (4). The slider (5) is designed such that both the specimen support (6) and additional weights (7) can be mounted. Its vertical axis is positioned using linear bearings (8).

The flat circular composite specimens were glued with epoxy adhesive to a mounting device (9) which rested in the specimen support. The epoxy adhesive was selected such that its shear strength is well above the anticipated frictional force being transferred between the sliding surfaces. Attention was paid to generate a very thin and evenly distributed adhesive film before mounting the composite samples. Thus, in the initial setup the sliding surfaces are coplanar and a collinear displacement along the sliding distance was achieved.

The slider is displaced using spindle drive (not shown) at 10 mm/s traversing velocity. The connection between the slider and the drive is equipped with a ball bearing and rubber elements. With the ball bearing in place, forces on the slider only act in displacement direction. The rubber

elements are positioned to damp possible vibrations initiated by the drive. This turned out to improve data quality at the onset of sliding friction.

Additionally, an electronic soft start device is implemented to allow for better data resolution when static friction is overcome.

The aluminium plate carries a flat composite base plate which is positioned against a bed-stop and kept in place using mounting supports (10). Thus, displacement of the CFRP base plate relative to the aluminium plate is minimised for the duration of each run.

The aluminium base plate is kept in place vertically by the ball bearings underneath and horizontally by bearings at both ends. At the far end (11) one of the bearings is attached to a spring such that the aluminium plate is restrained but not entirely clamped. At the near end, the base plate is directly attached via roller bearings to two load cells (2) measuring the frictional forces transmitted by sliding friction of the two substrates.

In order to obtain displacement data a wire potentiometer (12) is attached to the specimen support.

The sampling rate of the LabVIEW driven data acquisition is 70 Hz resulting in at least seven data points per mm sliding distance. Since a soft starting device is employed, there are more data points recorded at the beginning of each run. Hence, the data at the transition from static to kinetic friction is of higher resolution with respect to the sliding distance.

The coefficient of friction (μ) was calculated according to Equation (1). The frictional force (F_F)

Fig. 4. Side view of pin-on-flat test apparatus with sliding direction from right to left.

was derived using the load cell signals and the normal force (F_N), which was kept constant throughout all runs.

$$\mu = F_F / F_N \quad (1)$$

The test setup and its components were examined for measurement errors carefully. Considering the prospective results on the sliding friction response, the load cells with accuracy class of 0.1 were determined the most erroneous member in the measurement chain. With respect to the forces actually obtained, the coefficient of friction values presented here are reliable up to the second digit after the decimal point. However, for the sake of clarity some figures contain coefficient of friction data up to the third digit after the decimal point.

2.3 Testing Conditions

The parameters examined in this study are summarised in Tab. 1. Those include the texture orientation and operating fluids.

Tab. 1. Summary of examined parameters.

Examined parameter	Value
Texture orientation	0° / 45° / 90°
Operating fluids	De-icing fluid, engine oil

All experiments were executed at similar climate conditions as outlined in Tab. 2. Prior to testing, all specimens have at least been conditioned for three days at those laboratory conditions.

At the first stage, experiments with dry peel-ply textured surface samples were conducted. After reviewing the results, a configuration was selected to execute further tests incorporating aircraft operating fluids.

Tab. 2. Summary of environmental and testing conditions.

Factor	Condition / Value
Temperature	17.5 - 23.3 °C
Humidity	16.8 - 42.4%
Surface texture	Textured
Surface cleaning	Acetone, pressurised air
Debris	No initial debris
Lubrication	Operating fluids
Material	8552/AS4
Contact area	Circular, flat
System kinetics	Rigid linear guide
Vibration	No external vibration

Traversing velocity	10 mm/s
Normal force	127 N
Measurement technique	Load cells, wire potentiometer
Test classification	Pin-on-flat

The normal force and consequently the contact pressure were kept constant for all executed runs.

3 Results and Discussion

All bar charts in this section are formatted to the following convention: solid bars denote mean values and error bars indicate +/- one standard deviation. Dashed horizontal lines represent mean values and shaded areas symbolise +/- two standard deviations across all data not being grouped in configurations. The configurations are specified with respect to the sliding direction. Whilst the first denotes the CFRP base plate orientation, the second indicates the CFRP sample orientation.

In general, one type of response was observed. It is important to emphasise, as data analysis regarding the static coefficient of friction differs in consideration of the class of response [12].

Fig. 5 depicts the type of sliding friction response, where the static coefficient (μ_s) is higher compared to the kinetic coefficient of friction (μ_d). This response typically appeared for the samples with textured surface characteristic. The static friction coefficient was simple to determine, as it became evident by a sudden drop in the friction response.

Fig. 5. Coefficient of friction along sliding distance for a 0°-90° configuration textured surface specimens.

The kinetic coefficient of friction was determined using an ordinary least squares method [13]. In particular, linear polynomial regression was applied.

3.1 Dry Surface

The results of the dry textured surface specimens. For the configurations researched, the CFRP base plate was oriented in sliding direction. Consequently, the sample orientation was subject to variation.

The coefficient of friction results for textured surface specimens with varying sample orientation are presented in Fig. 6. The static coefficient is significantly higher compared to the kinetic coefficient of friction.

The coefficients of friction vary with the relative angle between base plate orientation and sample orientation. Yet, no clear trend can be observed.

The 0°-0° configuration shows the highest mean value and at the same time the biggest deviation between individual results. As the error bar of this specific setup overlaps with the error bars of the other configurations, the variations between the individual configurations are considered as not significant.

Therefore, the authors treated the data such that across all textured samples under dry sliding conditions the static coefficient of friction is determined as 0.60 ± 0.20 . The corresponding kinetic coefficient of friction is 0.47 ± 0.06 .

Fig. 6. Static (light grey) and kinetic (grey) coefficient of friction for textured surface specimens with varying texture orientation.

Wear was evident and measurable for the textured samples. The wear volume is calculated from the samples' weight loss, considering the resin properties specified in [7].

Fig. 7. Wear volume for textured surface specimens with varying texture orientation.

For each sample the weighing was repeated for three times to respect statistical deviations. The results are depicted in Fig. 7.

The wear volume did not vary considerably between the configurations investigated. Thus, it is determined across all specimens $0.63 \pm 0.15 \text{ mm}^3$.

Fig. 8. Peel-ply textured surface of 0°-90° configuration after testing. Sliding direction horizontally.

For the sliding conditions outlined, the governing wear mechanism affected the resin only. Fig. 8 shows a peel-ply textured surface specimens of a 0°-90° configuration after testing. The sliding direction was horizontally.

It is evident that exposed resin accumulations were worn. During the sliding process debris was collected in the resin recesses which were formed by the peel-ply weave style. To the authors interpretation, debris are the white agglomerations next to the sections of worn surface.

3.2 Contaminated Surface

Aircraft are operated with numerous fluids. Among many, two de-icing fluids (Kilfrost ABC K Plus, Kilfrost DF Plus) and one engine oil (BP Turbo Oil 2380) were selected for the current study.

For each run 1 ml of the respective fluid was evenly distributed on the CFRP base plate along the sliding distance using a brush. The circular samples were initially kept free of any contamination.

Exemplary, the peel-ply textured surface with Kilfrost DF Plus contamination prior to testing is shown in Fig. 9. The textured surface was sufficiently covered by the fluid executing the application procedure outlined above. Only the exposed resin accumulations stood out.

Fig. 9. Peel-ply textured surface with Kilfrost DF Plus contamination prior to testing.

After triggering the data acquisition, sample and base plate were put in contact. Thus, the static as well as the kinematic coefficient of friction were recorded under contamination conditions.

3.2.1 De-Icing fluid 1 – Kilfrost ABC K Plus

For Kilfrost ABC K Plus the sliding friction response is depicted in Fig. 10. The lubricating property becomes evident in the large drop between the static and the kinetic coefficient of friction.

Fig. 11 depicts the peel-ply textured surface of the 0°-90° configuration and Kilfrost ABC K Plus contamination after testing.

Due to the lubricating effect of the fluid applied, the worn surface sections are narrower compared to dry

friction setting. Only small debris agglomerations have formed during the test.

Fig. 10. Coefficient of friction along sliding distance for a 0°-90° configuration textured surface specimens and Kilfrost ABC K Plus contamination.

Fig. 11. Peel-ply textured surface of 0°-90° configuration and Kilfrost ABC K Plus contamination after testing. Sliding direction horizontally.

The static coefficient is determined as 0.54 ± 0.08 and the corresponding kinetic coefficient of friction is 0.20 ± 0.01 . The wear volume is $0.28 \pm 0.13 \text{ mm}^3$.

3.2.2 De-Icing fluid 2 – Kilfrost DF Plus

The sliding friction response for Kilfrost DF K Plus is depicted in Fig. 12. A lubricating property similar to de-icing fluid 1 is noticeable in the data shown. Although the difference in viscosity of both fluids is more than two orders of magnitude, the kinetic coefficient of friction was not affected.

Fig. 12. Coefficient of friction along sliding distance for a 0°-90° configuration textured surface specimens and Kilfrost DF Plus contamination.

The peel-ply textured surface of 0°-90° configuration and Kilfrost DF Plus contamination after testing is presented in Fig. 13. Albeit the sliding response is almost identical, the wear pattern is more obvious compared to the results of de-icing fluid 1.

Fig. 13. Peel-ply textured surface of 0°-90° configuration and Kilfrost DF Plus contamination after testing. Sliding direction horizontally.

However, Fig. 17 reveals large scatter in wear data obtained with de-icing fluid 2. Which indicates that any presented figure showing the wear pattern may not be perfectly representative. Nevertheless, for the sake of complete coverage Fig. 13 is provided. The static coefficient of friction is 0.55 ± 0.03 and the corresponding kinetic coefficient of friction observed is 0.22 ± 0.01 . The wear volume is $0.39 \pm 0.33 \text{ mm}^3$.

3.2.3 Engine oil – BP Turbo Oil 2380

The sliding friction response for a textured surface contaminated with BP Turbo Oil 2380 is provided in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Coefficient of friction along sliding distance for a 0°-90° configuration textured surface specimens and BP Turbo Oil 2380 contamination.

In general, the response is comparable to the previous operating fluids which were in essence water-based. With the current oil-based contamination, the lubricating effect on the static and kinetic coefficient of friction is slightly increased. Both values drop with respect to previous results.

Fig. 15. Peel-ply textured surface of 0°-90° configuration and BP Turbo Oil 2380 contamination after testing. Sliding direction horizontally.

In Fig. 15 the wear pattern after testing is shown. In contrast to the de-icing fluids, the oily contamination could not be removed after the test without further damage to the surface. Therefore, an oil film is still

present in the figure supplied. Consequently, wear debris is not clearly visible. Furthermore, any wear volume determination is without relevance. Hence, the static coefficient of friction is 0.52 ± 0.04 . The corresponding kinetic coefficient of friction received is 0.19 ± 0.02 , while the wear volume was not measurable.

3.2.4 Comparison to Dry Surface

The results of the measurements on textured samples with contamination by operating fluids are compared to the dry surface findings. All cases feature a 0° - 90° configuration.

Fig. 16 compares the static as well as the kinetic coefficients of friction. From the dry surface, via the water-based fluids, towards the oil-based contamination the static coefficient of friction decreases slightly but not significantly. Hence, for the investigated operating fluids there is no obvious decrease in the static coefficient of friction.

In contrast, a significant impact is obvious on the kinetic coefficient of friction. In the presence of operating fluids the lubricating effect reduces the kinetic coefficient of friction to about 50% of the initial value.

Fig. 16. Static (light grey) and kinetic (grey) coefficient of friction for textured surface specimens with varying surface contamination.

Examining the wear volume depicted in Fig. 17, when measurable the mean wear volume was reduced for contaminated textured surfaces. This coincides with the reduction in the respective kinetic friction coefficient.

Fig. 17. Wear volume for textured surface specimens with varying surface contamination.

However, determining the wear rate for contaminated samples was not trivial, as the contamination could not be removed residue-free in any case. Therefore, a large deviation for de-icing fluid 2 was observed. Furthermore, the wear volume determination for the engine oil contamination is without any relevance.

Tab. 3. Summary of coefficients of friction stating the mean value +/- two standard deviations.

Surface state	Contamination state	μ_s	μ_d
All configurations			
Textured	Dry	0.60 ± 0.20	0.47 ± 0.06
Only 0° - 90° configuration			
Textured	Dry	0.58 ± 0.07	0.46 ± 0.07
Textured	De-icing 1	0.54 ± 0.08	0.20 ± 0.01
Textured	De-icing 2	0.55 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.01
Textured	Engine oil	0.52 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.02

Finally, Tab. 3 summarises the coefficients of friction acquired in this study.

4 Conclusion

This paper provides experimental data novel in the field of polymer-on-polymer friction. The pin-on-flat sliding friction results are presented for surface textured CFRP specimens with and without contamination by aircraft operating fluids. The findings are summarised as:

1. Epoxy resin peel-ply textured surfaces under dry sliding conditions exhibit a static coefficient of friction of 0.60 ± 0.20 , a kinetic coefficient of

friction of 0.47 ± 0.06 , and a wear volume of $0.63 \pm 0.15 \text{ mm}^3$.

2. Contamination by aircraft operating fluids, such as de-icing fluids and engine oil, decreases the kinetic coefficient of friction to about 50% of the initial value. Due to the lubricating effect the wear volume is diminished. Specifying the wear volume reduction, however, was not trivial as the contamination could not be removed residue-free in any case.

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References

- [1] EASA “*Certification specifications for large aeroplanes cs-25*”. European Aviation Safety Agency, 2003.
- [2] K.C. Ludema “*Friction, Wear, Lubrication: A Textbook in Tribology*”. Taylor & Francis, 2010.
- [3] X.H. Zhou, Y.S. Sun and W.S. Wang “Influences of carbon fabric/epoxy composites fabrication process on its friction and wear properties”. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 209, No. 9, pp 4553-4557, 2009.
- [4] K. Friedrich and A.K. Schlarb “*Tribology of Polymeric Nanocomposites: Friction and Wear of Bulk Materials and Coatings*”. Elsevier Science, 2011.
- [5] G.M. Bartenev and V.V. Lavrentev “*Friction and Wear of Polymers*”. Elsevier Science, 1981.
- [6] J. Schön “Coefficient of friction and wear of a carbon fiber epoxy matrix composite”. *Wear*, Vol. 257, No. 3-4, pp 395-407, 2004.
- [7] “HexPly[®] 8552 epoxy matrix – product data”. Hexcel Composites Publication, 2012.
- [8] “HexForce[®] T0089 peel ply – product data”. Hexcel Aerospace Selector Guide, 2001.
- [9] ASTM D1894 “*Standard Test Method for Static and Kinetic Coefficients of Friction of Plastic Film and Sheeting*”. ASTM International, 2011.
- [10] D. Stefaniak, E. Kappel, T. Spröwitz and C. Hühne “Experimental identification of process parameters inducing warpage of autoclave-processed CFRP parts”. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 43, No. 7, pp 1081-1091, 2012.
- [11] E. Kappel, D. Stefaniak, T. Spröwitz and C. Hühne “A semi-analytical simulation strategy and its application to warpage of autoclave-processed CFRP parts”. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 42, No. 12, pp 1985-1994, 2011.
- [12] K.G. Budinski “*MNL 56 guide to friction, wear, and erosion testing*”. ASTM International, 2007.
- [13] P. T. Boggs and J. E. Rogers “*Orthogonal Distance Regression*” in “*Statistical analysis of measurement error models and applications: proceedings of the AMS-IMS-SIAM joint summer research conference held June 10-16, 1989,*” Contemporary Mathematics, vol. 112, pg. 186, 1990.